

Take action to support preprints

Have 5 minutes?

- Tweet the last preprint you read, retweet a colleague's post about their preprint
- Set up an [email alert](#) to a preprint server
- Sign up to a [newsletter](#) listing recently posted preprints mentioned on Twitter
- Choose a [sticker](#) or share an [ASAPbio infographic](#)

Have 30 minutes?

- Read a preprint
- Write a Twitter thread about a preprint discussing the study's findings
- Organize a discussion in your next lab meeting about pros and cons of preprinting your work

Have 2 hours?

- Review a preprint and post your review publicly
- Participate in a podcast e.g. [Preprints in Motion](#)
- Write a blog post about your interest in preprints, or about the last preprint you read
- Invite the author of a preprint to present at your journal club or at your institution

Want to learn more?

- Check the ASAPbio website asapbio.org for upcoming events about preprints or sign up to the ASAPbio newsletter: asapbio.org/newsletter

- Visit ASAPbio's Preprint resource centre for preprint resources, infographics, preprint FAQ and more: asapbio.org/preprint-info

Get involved

- Join the ASAPbio Community at tinyurl.com/ASAPbio
- Join a [PREreview](#) live-streamed preprint journal club
- Join [preLights](#), a community of early career researchers who write highlights about preprints

Infographic by ASAPbio Fellows: Umar Ahmad, Christine Ferguson and Sumeet Pal Singh